

APPLYING SHADOWING TECHNIQUE AND AUTHENTIC MATERIALS TO PROMOTE PHONOLOGICAL AWARENESS AMONG YOUNG LEARNERS OF ENGLISH

Nguyen Hong Oanh^{1*}, Nguyen Minh Tri^{2**}

¹Banking University of Ho Chi Minh City

²Nguyen Tat Thanh University

Email: *oanhnh@buh.edu.vn, **tringuyen.eling@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Over the years, there have been various teaching methods, and approaches introduced and then applied in teaching English language. Among them, shadowing techniques have been widely used for many years, and authentic materials have also proved to assist learners greatly in their second language acquisition process. Over their time teaching at university, the researchers have been persuaded that the more exposure students have to language as spoken and used by native speakers, the better they would become in their communication. This proves to be of great importance when it comes to young learners' acquisition of the language. This belief has shed a light to this research paper.

This paper aims at investigating the effectiveness of applying shadowing techniques and authentic materials to promote phonological awareness among young learners of English. The study was conducted within the period of 8 weeks in a class of 40 young learners at grade 5 whose language proficiency ranged from A1 – A2 according to Common European Framework for Reference (CEFR). The data were collected via a variety of qualitative and quantitative tools inclusive of interview, survey, and classroom portfolio. The findings revealed that authentic materials that were gathered from updated and trendy conversation situations accelerated learners' engagement and applicability in practice while shadowing techniques contributed to enhancing students' phonological correctness, self-confidence, and fluency in daily communication. As a result, the combination of two techniques together played a role in optimizing classroom activities in teaching pronunciation for younger learners in the presence of an optimistic environment...

1 INTRODUCTION

Language is an undeniably indispensable part of human daily life and communication. Individuals communicate with one another so as to create, express, and interpret meanings in conversational exchange contexts. In addition, social and interpersonal relationships cannot be established and maintained over time without the mutual understanding of both partners' messages in both spoken and written form. This requires not only the development of the awareness of the language in terms of grammatical forms and phonetic/phonemic characteristics of the target language.

In 1999, Nunan, in his prestigious book on second language teaching and learning, declared that in order to communicate successfully, language learners necessarily acquire not only specific

properties of language such as grammar, pronunciation and vocabulary (i.e. linguistic competence) but also the method to elaborate the linguistic messages (i.e. socio-linguistic competence).

Spoken language is, to some certain extent, of great difference with written form. The distinct divergence can be in the wide range from grammatical structures to lexical resources and discourse patterns. Spoken utterances can be mistaken on a frequent basis due to either the alteration in the sound pronounced or the misplaced stresses. Therefore, phonological awareness can significantly assist learners in achieving their communicative purposes, regardless of the command of their English.

Researchers in language teaching and acquisition accentuates the important role of materials employed in classroom contexts to achieve the aforementioned conversational purposes as the authenticity and practicality encourage learners to be fully engaged in the process of examining, evaluating, and applying the language input from phonological to semantic perception. With young learners, teachers have adopted the shadowing technique in combination with real-life materials in their lesson planning and delivery to maximize the effectiveness of the input.

Given the limited time and participant in the research, researchers have attempted to crystalize the influential role of the combination of shadowing technique and authentic materials in enhancing young learners' communicative skills in terms of their pronunciation, fluency, and self-confidence.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The concept of shadowing technique

Roughly spoken, shadowing means mimicking. This technique is used by those who want to adopt the conversational style of a particular person. Also known as shadowing reading or shadowing listening, this involves language learners “speak along” in time with an audio text (Hamada, 2015), which shares some common features with karaoke singing except that with song singing along, one can have the words in the front. The implication of shadowing is that one’s shadow follows every movement he/she makes. Similarly, language learners will shadow or echo what is heard as coincidentally and precisely as possible. This process was illustrated by Hamada (2018) as follows:

Time:	----->
Audio stimulus:	Shadowing is not as easy as it seems.
Learners:	Shadowing is not as easy as it seems.

As can be seen from the illustration, the learners start reflecting the language input exactly after they hear and maintain the task until the speech reaches the end.

On the other hand, with repetition, Hamada (2018) generalized as

Time:	----->
Audio stimulus:	Shadowing is not as easy as....
Learners:	Shadowing is not as easy as....

With repetition or echoing, learners tend to repeat the words while stimulating their episodic memory by storing as many words as possible. The silent time lapse between input reception and reflection indicates that repetition can be regarded as an off-line task while shadowing is online because of the prompt process of verbal expressions. Therefore, shadowing is actually cognitive and active activities that place more emphasis on phonetic aspects of the target language. The claim has consolidated Tamai's comments (1997) on the learners' reaction towards the speech while listening.

However, shadowing technique was not initially developed for the purpose of language acquisition and practice. In contrast, it was one of the effective techniques to train interpreters in Europe (Kurz, 1992). As language teachers observed the effectiveness of this technique in improving interpreters' listening and speaking skills alongside with the ability to simultaneously adapt and react, they have reached a decision to add this training technique to their lists of teaching activities and approaches. Kadota (2007) addressed that while shadowing, students focus more on their speech perception as they have to evaluate and transfer the audio text without any silent gap before uttering. The spontaneity enables learners to pay greater attention to the phonological aspects of the language while shadowing, in comparison with the off-line task of repetition where they have enough time to process the input before producing the utterances (Shiki, Mori, Kadota, & Yoshita, 2010). This immediate reflection trains the phonological loops, which, in turn, comprises part of their working memory to serve the communication (Baddeley, 2007). The phonological loop processes and stores the take-in, then retains for two seconds in the phonological short-term memory to prepare for the sub-vocal rehearsals. The improvement in short-term memory capacity can be of great assistance for language learners, especially young ones to master the language.

Language teachers who intend to adopt this training technique in their practical classroom settings need to know how researchers have further classified shadowing technique into sub-types. The central issue stated here is that the pedagogical implementation should be based on the nature of each analytical categorization. In examining the length of the information being heard and echoed, Nicholson (1990) suggested that shadowing can be in different forms such as phonemic, phrase and lag shadowing. The distinction has been drawn from the difference in the amount of linguistic repetition, ranging from individual words, to longer phrases to almost complete sentences. In phrase shadowing, learners are allowed to pause sometime before shadowing in order to clarify the delivered message. The most problematic type of shadowing in this taxonomy may be adjusted lag shadowing, where the listeners must consistently maintain five to seven, or even ten words behind the speakers.

Later in 1995, Murphey published a book that demonstrated another way to sub-group shadowing. From his logical elaboration, the technique can be found in different forms such as lecture shadowing, reading shadowing and conversational shadowing. In this backdrop, shadowing was discussed under the aim of teaching procedures and various activities. With lecture shadowing, learners or shadowers echo silently in their heads what a speaker says. In other forms, shadowing can be done silently or with uttered sounds to a certain extent. In reading shadowing, shadowers read a text while their partners mirrors the words.

Furthermore, Murphey (2001) modified his own grouping method and suggested shadowing can be divided into complete, selective and interactive shadowing. His later division was mainly based on how much of the perceived messages are repeated. If the learners mimick everything the speakers say, then they are practicing the complete shadowing process. On the other hand, if shadowers, as instructed in the task, only choose to repeat certain words or phrases, they are selectively mirroring the text. In a more advanced type, learners demonstrate two concurrently actions, i.e. they choose

a specific part of the input exactly before adding their own questions and comments or personal reflection in order to make it more natural.

Another important classification method was depicted by Kadota and Tamai (2005) in the work on Ketteiban Shadowing English in Japan. According to these two scholars, shadowing can be classified as mumbling, synchronal reading, prosody shadowing and content shadowing. In the first type of shadowing, learners principally target the listening passages. With synchronal reading, the learners are provided with a manuscript so that they can immediately follow the speakers by reading aloud and stimulating every sound and intonation. An additional step in synchronized shadowing takes place when listeners shadow the reading text without the assistance of the script. The last type in these two researchers' classification puts equal concentration on both the sound and the content of the speech.

In the light of these grouping practices, shadowing technique has been observed and supported with evidence to significantly improve language learners' listening skills. Moreover, this approach should be considered as a useful source of assistance for lower-level learners in enhancing their communication skills. Hamada (2015) pointed out that five times shadowing of a particular phrase is most beneficial for language acquisition. Before and after the shadowing activities, other tasks should be completed to guarantee the understanding and familiarity with the topic.

However, there are certain drawbacks to applying shadowing technique in teaching English as a second language as it has been handled with the available textbooks assigned for particular language educational frameworks. As consequence, this study analyzes the influential benefits of its application in contact with more authentic materials in order to maximize its effectiveness in enhancing learners' communication skills from the point of phonological awareness. This can be explained by the intention of applying shadowing in teaching language was to allow learner build a connection between real phonological realisations of words and their orthographical forms and meanings, especially where weak forms, elision and assimilation exist (Hamada, 2015).

2.2 The role of authentic materials

The ultimate objective in language teaching process is to enable learners to master the target language; therefore, language teachers always manage to diversify their teaching material on the basis of vitality, authenticity, and applicability. Rogers and Medley (1988) asserted that authentic materials expose the genuineness and naturalness of the language and well-contextualised in the native speakers' settings. Later, Harmer (1991), in his book "The Practice of English Language Teaching", considered that authentic texts are "real designed not for language students, but for speakers of the language in questions'.

Moreover, Wong, Kwok and Choi (1995) claimed that the authenticity of materials needs to be identified by the time, people, and locations. In other words, these materials are used in the country where the target language is spoken, by the people inhabited there and in the current circumstances of utterance. Nunan (1999) added that spoken and written authentic texts have been produced in the course of genuine communication, not specifically written for purposes of language teaching. In general, within the context of this study, we conclude that authentic materials are real and exist in the real communication of the target language, used by the native speakers in their daily life and not produced for training purposes.

In spite of the unintentionally designed for teaching purposes, authentic materials have gained much attention to be applied in teaching and learning language, especially in teaching English as a second language. The source of authentic materials that can be used in classroom contexts is

diverse and can match different teaching and learning purposes. Oura (2001) cited Gerbhard (1996) that authentic materials vary in types, ranging from listening materials such as radio show, songs or podcasts, visual materials like TV shows or movies, printed materials, for example, magazines, posters, and maps to realia or real-world objects like apples or cars or even things at the playgrounds. Furthermore, in the era of technology, authentic materials can also be categorized as online and printed materials. The former which is continuously updated, more visually appealing and more interactive plays as an important role in teaching language communicatively. The latter are described as quickly dated form of teaching and learning materials with some representatives such as newspapers, literature works and songs.

Many scholars have analyzed the use of authentic materials in classroom activities. These materials have positively affected students' language acquisition as they offer learners more chances to interact with the real language ad content rather than its form (Berado, 2006). The authenticity in these real materials can make up for the imperfection of non-authentic materials such as textbooks as the "false" versions are planned, designed and produced in accordance with the educational curriculum and policy in each country. The non-authentic ones are built on the assumption of learners' level of language command, needs and ability; which, therefore, lacks the practicality and spontaneity.

Thanajaro (2000) and Otte (2006) both shared the similar perspective that authentic materials improve learners' self-satisfaction and motivation after they are employed in classroom practice because these materials provide them with the "real" language as it is used and conversed in real world outside the classroom. Taking this scenario into consideration, Al Azri and Al-Rashdi (2014) justified the inappropriate teaching materials can cause learners to suffer from difficulties in learning a foreign language since learners should be motivated to acquire and master any language in communication for informational and social exchange purposes.

Peacock (1997) as cited in Richard (2001) listed several reasons for using authentic materials in educational contexts. They are: (1) preparation for real life; (2) learners' necessary satisfaction; (3) source of positive motivation; (4) source of encouragement for teachers to adopt effective teaching methods; (5) authentic information about the culture of the people speaking the target language. For these reasons, authentic materials help build linguistic gaps between the language presented in the class and that used in daily situations.

2.3 The significance of phonological awareness

Phonological awareness is sometimes mistaken as phonemic awareness, which needs to be correctly understood as one small aspect of the earlier mentioned term. Phonological awareness itself is part of a bigger notion known as metalinguistic awareness. Though these two terms are sometimes used interchangeably, they are slightly different in meanings. Phonological awareness is the superordinate term which involves that of different sound aspects of a particular language. On the other hand, phonemic awareness is more specific in that it informs about the ability to identify each phoneme, i.e. the smallest unit of speech in words (Chapman, 2003).

Moat (2000) defined phonological awareness as "the conscious awareness that words are made up segments of our own speech that are represented with letters in an alphabetic orthography". For this reason, children who successfully develop awareness can identify and produce rhymes, match sounds to words, and break words into sound units. Sensenbaugh (2000) proclaimed that this ability can best predict the ease of early reading acquisition, which leads to better absorption of input information in longer term.

The important implication from the understanding of metalinguistic concepts is that children as young learners of any particular language can build a strong foundation in the word spelling and its relationship with oral language. This type of foundation involves the alphabet principle (that is the relationship between alphabetical letters and speech sounds), the phonetic principle (or the relationships between speech sound patterns and letter patterns), and phonological awareness (i.e. that of sound dimension of oral language) (Chapman, 2003).

Phonological awareness, as analyzed by Ehri and Nunes (2002), can comprise of the abilities to identify alliteration, rhyming words, word boundaries, and word components, for example: syllables, initials and onsets, endings, and phonemes. Language learners who can develop phonological awareness are able to divide words into phonemes and put those phonemes back into words. These two opposite processes have extensive contribution to learners' literacy competence as well as oral skills because they are familiar with word blending and word sounding patterns.

Phonological awareness deals with oral language that allows language learners to think the sounds in a word (i.e. the word's phonological structure) rather than just its meaning. Moreover, phonological awareness is the understanding of the structure of spoken language – which it is made up of words, and words consist of syllables, rhymes, and sounds. Fitzpatrick (1997) summarized it best by saying that phonological awareness. In the later process, they look for familiar "letter patterns" as one strategy when attempting to decode or spell unfamiliar words – they use familiar sound chunks from known words, not just individual sounds. In other words, students look for "pronounceable word parts". This "chunking" of sounds makes the reading and spelling process much more effective and efficient. These letter patterns are based on familiar syllable or rhyme patterns as well as sound clusters and individual sounds. To be successful in using letter-sound knowledge in reading and writing, learners need to know how to segment and manipulate syllables, onset and rhyme and sounds. With these phonetic knowledge and skills, learners can speak better with a more natural accent.

In presence of the aforementioned elements, researchers aim to investigate a case study with the following question:

What are the impacts of combining shadowing technique and authentic materials on learners' phonological awareness?

3 THE STUDY

3.1 The study design and participants

The study was conducted throughout a period of eight weeks in a class of 40 young learners at grade 5 at an English center where they attended the course as a separate additional course from their school. Learners' language proficiency ranged from A1 to A2 in Common European Framework for Reference. They attended the classes for two days of the week and two lessons of two hours were delivered a day. In the study, in total of 20 videos and audio recordings were adopted from authentic sources of Youtube whose contents were related to basic daily communication. In addition, shadowing technique was applied with the assistance of authentic materials to aim at teaching pronunciation.

Method: A combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches was applied during the study to investigate the improvement of two new teaching methods on communicative competence.

3.2 Data collection

Diagnostic assessment: At the beginning of the course, a mini diagnostic test was conducted to assess learners’ speaking skill with four criteria of fluency and coherence, grammatical range and accuracy, lexical resource, and pronunciation.

Portfolio: All learners’ activities were carefully observed and their mistakes or weaknesses in pronunciation were noted for consideration of the development during the course. Furthermore, the portfolio served as an additional tool of formative assessment during the investigation

Survey: A survey of 20 questions was delivered to students in regard to their attitude toward authentic materials and the impacts of the combination between authentic material and shadowing technique. Also, the translated versions of the questions were added due to the young age of participants.

4 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

On purpose of investigating the impact of combing shadowing technique and authentic material on learners’ phonological awareness in oral communicative competence, two tests were delivered in advance of the beginning and at the end of the course with the results below

Figure 1. The deviation of learners' performance after the study

The study showed positive impacts on young learners’ oral performance after the innovative implementation. As can be seen from the chart, the majority of students had better academic results at 65% while a fifth of participants experienced an increase after the investigation. In addition, it is noticeable that the proportion of students with no difference was 15%. In brief, the combination of shadowing technique and authentic material brought about a dramatic positive impact on students’ communicative performance during the course of study.

The results of paired sample T-test after the study

Table 1: The comparison of learners’ performance before and after the intervention

Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Pre-test	40	1.210	.191
	Post-test	40	1.176	.186

Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Pre-test - Post-test	-.600	1.194	.189	-.982	-.218	-3.178	39	.003

According to the provided data, after the study most students showed higher performance which was represented in the post-test’s mean at 6.45 higher than 5.85 in the pre-test. Furthermore, the results indicate that sig. was $0.003 < 0.05$. The mean after the implementation illustrates the acceptable result above average score of the study to raise participants’ overall scores after the course at the center. The data suggest that the combination of shadowing technique and authentic material had significant influence on students’ communicative competence at young ages.

The impacts of shadowing technique and authentic material on young learners’ phonological awareness

Figure 2. The percentage of improvement after the implementation

The study indicates many positive effects on young learners’ phonological awareness. First of all, the highest percentage of improvement belonged to stress at 85% while the level of naturalness stood at the lowest point of 55%. Stress was considered to be the least difficult element in pronunciation as it was only necessary for learners to memorize the rules of stress in different syllables and they were able to pronounce correctly. On the contrary, the main reason why students had to deal with a large number of troubles to speak naturally was that they were unable to get exposure to real daily speaking context and the time of applying authentic material was limited for individuals. Hence only a rough half of the whole class changed their ways of producing natural utterances in a natural manner.

Furthermore, intonation occupied 80% of the class in improvement. Learners imitated the way people practiced and performed speaking in the videos and they tried to read out repeatedly with the similar intonation and they were allowed to practice various contextual shadowing of one sentence. As a result, they could realize the key words which played the most significant role in the whole utterance.

Most importantly, the percentage of exponents and consonants were equal at 72.5%. In theory-based lesson delivery, teacher introduced the meaning and the role of the words and sentences to the whole class and videos helped them to cognize the function of an utterance in specific situations in reality. Therefore, students could dramatically remember the function and the meaning of the words they would use in communication. Meanwhile, English consonants shared some similarities in oral shape and phonological constitution with their mother tongue of Vietnamese. Thus, it was easier for them to realize and single out the correct pronunciation of English consonants. In contrast, they also faced some difficulties in pronouncing subordinate consonants, especially endings sounds.

In addition, the proportion of students who showed improvement in stress was 70%. Learners were able to recognize and imitate a number of primary monophthongs and basically shaped their mouths in pronunciation from daily items and instruments. The repetition allowed them to read out loud those phonemes and they could correct gradually with the assistance of teacher. However, it was pretty hard for most of them to fix their diphthongs and triphthongs because they could not adopt the differences between pronouncing one sound and combining two or three sounds at the same time. It resulted in the hilarious and separate pronunciation of each vowel.

Moreover, phonetic variants accounted for 67.5 % while idea clarity was lower by 5%. Thanks to the presence of authentic videos to provide learners with real communicative situations, they were able to recognize the changes in pronunciation of some words in comparison with the dictionary to produce more natural and intensive utterances. Whilst, learners could improve the way they expressed their emotions and ideas by imitating the voice in the recording to imitate; however, they could not fully show how they feel or think about an entity.

Additionally, it is worth pointing out that 60% of young learners in the case study could improve their connected speech and silent sounds. The connection between two words was considerably inserted into their speech after they listened carefully from the recording and they could also raise their awareness of the absence of some sounds in certain words which were different from written forms. Thus, students delivered their ideas in a more comprehensive way.

PEDAGOGICAL IMPLICATION AND LIMITATION

The case study indicated a large number of applications in practical teaching contexts for young learners. First, the previous teaching approach regularly adopted the recording from textbooks or authentic tests which were absolutely modified to deal with the format of an international test. And, they could not utterly create practice-based situations for learners to practice speaking. As a result, it was difficult for learners to communicate in reality. The study proved the effectiveness of the combination of shadowing technique and authentic material on young learners' phonological awareness. Via the implementation of the new teaching technique focusing in articulation, learners could highly realize and memorize the similarities and differences of the phonetic components in practical communication. Therefore, they could minimize the ambiguity in pronunciation of some consonants and sounds which were strongly identical to express. Second, shadowing technique created an opportunity for young learners to be confident to practice and pronounce their speech in

a more comfortable and pleasant way. Thanks to the availability of the authentic material, they could imitate the models of practice and then autonomously realize fix their mistakes at the same time. Finally, learners could raise their sense of naturalness in communication, which allowed them to actively participate in other classroom activities and find engagement in the authentic material.

Nonetheless, the study had to confront with some limitations. The size of participants was quite small, which to some extent affected the outcomes of the study and the generalization of the whole study to cover other groups of participants which had various features. Moreover, the amount of time was limited in eight weeks, then the study could not investigate the intervention of other elements in the process of applying new teaching techniques such as learners' personal traits or learning autonomy after class. Hence, the findings of this study are only applicable for similar teaching contexts of the investigation.

5 CONCLUSION

The study has addressed a number of significant impacts of the combination of shadowing technique and authentic material on learners' phonological awareness. First, the whole participants showed their dramatic improvements in academic performance of communicative competence. Learners were able to realize and cope with authentic speaking context to raise their awareness of articulation and phonological expressions. Second, it is notable that some special modifications in communication such as phonetic variants or silent sounds were fixed during the implementation. This study serves as one fundamental component in teaching speaking skills. It is recommended that more studies should be conducted to investigate how information technology and other attributes such as learning motivation or teachers' qualification intervene this new implementation.

REFERENCE

- [1] Al Azri, R. H., & Al-Rashdi, M. H. (2014). The effect of using authentic materials in teaching. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 3 (10), 249-254.
- [2] Baddeley, A. (2007). *Working memory, thought, and action*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [3] Berardo, S. A. (2006). The use of authentic materials in the teaching of reading. *The reading Matrix*, 6 (2), 60-69.
- [4] Chapman, M. L. (2003). Phonemic Awareness: Clarifying What We Know. *Literacy Teaching and Learning*, Volume 7, Numbers1&2, 91-114.
- [5] Ehri, L. & Nunes, S. R. (2002). The role of phonemic awareness in learning to read. In A Farstrup & S. J. Samuels (Eds.), *What research has to say about reading instruction* (3rd ed.) (pp. 110-139). Newark, DE: International Reading Association.
- [6] Fitzpatrick, J. *Phonemic Awareness: Playing With Sounds to Strengthen Beginning Reading Skills*. Creative Teaching Press, 1997.
- [7] Gilmore, A. (2007). Authentic materials and authenticity in foreign language learning. *Language Teaching*, 40, 97-118.
- [8] Hamada, Y. (2015), 'Shadowing: Who benefits and how? Uncovering a booming EFL teaching technique for listening comprehension', *Language Teaching Research*, Vol 20 / 1, pp. 35 – 52.

- [9] Hamada, Y. (2018). Monitoring strategy in shadowing: Self-monitoring and pair-monitoring. *TESL Ontario*, 44, 19-24.
- [10] Harmer, J. 1994. *The Practice of English Language Teaching*. London: Longman.
- [11] Kadota, S., & Tamai, K. (2005). *Ketteiban Eigo Shadowing [English shadowing]*. Tokyo: Cosmopier Publishing Company.
- [12] Kadota, S. (2007). *Shadowing to ondoku no kagaku [Science of shadowing and oral reading]*. Tokyo: Cosmopier.
- [13] Kurz, I. (1992). "Shadowing' Exercises In Interpreter Training". In Dollerup, C. and Loddegaard, A.(eds), 245-250.
- [14] Moats, L. (2000). *Speech to print: Language essentials for teachers*. Baltimore, MD: Brooks Publishing
- [15] Murphey, T. 1995: Conversational shadowing for rapport and interactional language acquisition. In *Proceedings of the 6th Conference on Second Language Research in Japan*. International University of Japan, 42-65.
- [16] Murphey, Tim. (2001). Exploring conversational shadowing. *Language Teaching Research - LANG TEACH RES*. 5. 128-155. 10.1177/136216880100500203.
- [17] Nicholson, N. (1990). Strategy, innovation and performance. *Journal of Management Studies*, 27(5), 511–534. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6486.1990.tb00259.x>
- [18] Nunan, D. (1999). *Second Language Teaching and Learning*. Boston: Heinle and Heinle Publishers.
- [19] Otte, J. (2006). *Real language to real people: a descriptive and exploratory case study of the outcomes of aural authentic texts on the listening comprehension of adult ESL students enrolled in an advanced ESL listening course*. Dissertation Abstracts International
- [20] Peacock, M. (1997). The effect of authentic materials on the motivation of EFL learners, *ELT Journal: English Language Teachers Journal* 51 (2) 144–156
- [21] Shiki, Mori, Kadota, & Yoshita. (2010). Exploring Differences Between Shadowing and Repeating Practices: An Analysis of Reproduction Rate and Types of Reproduced Words. *The Japan Society of English Language Education*, 21, 81-90
- [22] Tamai, K. (1997). Shadowing no koka to chokai process ni okeru ichizuke [The effectiveness of shadowing and its position in the listening process]. *Current English Studies*, 36, 105–116.
- [23] Wong, V., Kwok, P. & Choi, N (1995). The use of authentic materials at tertiary level. *ELT journal*, 49 (4), 318-322.